

14th AFRAS COLLOQUIUM

The 14th African Arachnological Society of Africa was hosted by the Arachnology Unit of the Agricultural Research Council – Plant Health and Protection at ATKV Buffelspoort Resort, Rustenburg, North West Province, South Africa from 28th January - 1st February 2024.

- The Colloquium was organized by Robin Lyle of the Agricultural Research Council with the assistance of Petro Marais, Maggie Manyatsa, Eugene Madiseng and Piet van Niekerk.
- It was attended by 23 delegates with Dr Rudy Jocqué and his wife Elizabeth coming from Belgium and Carol Kunene from Kenya.
- A total of 15 papers and 6 posters were presented over a two day period.
- A memorial service on the morning of the 29th January 2024 was held in memory of the late Dr. Stefan Foord. An obituary was delivered by Dr. Caswell Munyai and a slide show about his life by Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman and Robin Lyle. During the event, delegates signed a Book of Condolences (see also page 2).
- The late Peter Webb who died in 1922 was also remembered.
- During the plenary Talk “SANSa after 27 years: The present status of spiders in South Africa” the success of the South African National Survey of Arachnida was discussed. South Africa now have a updated detailed checklist listing 2300 species as well as a Red List for all the species. A magnitude of information has been published in >500 scientific papers and books.
- During the African Arachnida Society (AFRAS) meeting a slide show was presented reflecting on the history of AFRAS which was initiated in 1986. The main aim of AFRAS is to promote Arachnological research in Africa.

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COLLOQUIUM

STEFAN FOORD – WE LOST A GREAT ARACHNOLOGIST AND FRIEND

One of South Africa's much loved and well-known arachnologists, "Stefan Foord", passed away on Thursday 21 December 2023, aged 52. At the time of his passing, he was the NRF-SARChI Chair in Biodiversity Value and Change at the University of Venda in South Africa, and was the sitting Chairperson of the African Arachnological Society (AFRAS). He was a prolific ecologist and did a lot of pioneering work on the biodiversity and ecology of spiders in South Africa and played an important role in the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa). He was a core member of SANSa and instrumental in:

- Preparation of the First Atlas of South African Spiders (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010).
- Red List of South African Spiders (Foord *et al.*, 2020).
- The 2023 South African national spider checklist (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023).
- Responsible for all the species distribution maps of SANSa.
- Responsible for the long-term surveys (6 years) funded by the Centre of Invasion Biology (CIB) that took place at two sites in South Africa.
- As a core member of SANSa he managed and undertook numerous surveys in the Savanna Biome that resulted in a book on the biome.
- Co-authored the 60 photo identification guides that are available online.
- Involved in project funded by the NRF under the SARChI chair in Biodiversity and Value and the DFG (German Research Foundation) as part of the SALLnet research project
- He was also involved in the SPACES (Scientific Partnerships for Complex Earth Systems) program funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF), to study spider communities in and around villages using pitfall traps.
- He was supervisor to a broad array of postgraduate students and, more recently, postdoctoral fellows, and made a massive contribution to the development of arachnology in Africa.
- He also made a significant contribution to the systematics of Afrotropical spiders and described or co-authored the description of 29 spider species during his career. He revised the Hersiliidae and with Dr. Galina Azarkina (Russia) a project was registered to study some Salticidae genera.
- Stefan was a prolific researcher who is best known for his publications on the ecology of South African spiders especially in the Limpopo Province. He was the author and co-author of more than 100 journal articles, one book chapter, and two books.

Dr. Galina Azarkina (Russia) and Stefan Foord

Stefan Foord and the Venda team out to collect

His colourful presence will be missed for many years to come, but his enthusiasm will continue to inspire us. But at least we will remember him by all the species named after him:

- *Bastanius foordi* (Marusik & Fet, 2009) [HERSILIIDAE]
- *Cheiracanthium foordi* Lotz, 2015 [CHEIRACANTHIIDAE]
- *Propiomarengo foordi* Azarkina & Haddad, 2020 [SALTICIDAE]
- *Diphya foordi* Omelko, Marusik & Lyle, 2020 [TETRAGNATHIDAE]
- *Yimbulunga foordi* Wesolowska, Azarkina & Russell-Smith, 2014 [SALTICIDAE]
- *Heriaeus foordi* Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013 [THOMISIDAE]

A GEDENKSCHRIFT FOR STEFAN THAT WILL BE PUBLISHED IN THE JOURNAL AFRICAN INVERTEBRATES IN DECEMBER 2024. SEE P. 34.

14TH AFRAS COLLOQUIUM AWARDS

The Lawrence Award is made to people that have made important contributions to arachnid research in Africa. Two people were awarded the **Lawrence Award** this year at the 14th AFRAS Colloquium.

Stefan was a prolific ecologist and did a lot of pioneering work on the biodiversity and ecology of spiders in South Africa and has published >100 papers and trained numerous students.

- He was a core member of SANSa.
- Team leader of the Venda team.
- Responsible for the long-term surveys funded by the Centre of Invasion Biology (CIB).
- Member of the South African Red Listing of Spiders.
- Responsible for GAP analyses and all the distribution maps of SANSa.
- As an ecologist he was responsible for all the statistical analyses.
- He was appointed by the NRF to the SARChI Chair: Biodiversity Value and Change in the Vhembe Reserve, University of Venda (2022-2023).
- NRF-rated scientist.

Charles is a taxonomist by excellence and has described >200 species of South Africa spiders but also as an ecologist and he extensively sampled spiders contributing to their biodiversity and ecology.

- He is a core member of SANSa.
- Team leader of the Free State team.
- He has published >150 papers.
- Trained numerous students.
- Member of the South African Red Listing of Spiders.
- Excellent field worker and he did a lot of pioneering work on the biodiversity and ecology of spiders in the Free State, KwaZulu-Natal, Northern and Western Cape.
- Project leader of several NRF projects.
- NRF rated scientist.

COLLOQUIUM: BEST PAPER

An update on the current state of South African pseudoscorpion taxonomy

J.A. Neethling

Despite recent taxonomic revisions and phylogenetic analysis, detailed morphological and ecological data is still lacking for the vast majority of pseudoscorpions, including the poorly-known South African fauna. South Africa currently has 162 known species in 17 families, with over 70% of these species endemic to the country. Early research on the South African Pseudoscorpiones fauna primarily consisted of taxonomic descriptions and, apart from a few local contributions, most of the research was conducted by foreign scientists. When they retired, taxonomic descriptions of new species ceased. Later research includes the publication of a species checklist and contributions to karyotype studies and phylogenetic analyses. The need for detailed revisions of our indigenous fauna was recognized, and in 2017 the first article was published, revising the South African Geogarypiidae. The second article, on the revision of the South African Gymnobiidae, has been submitted for publication in 2023. Future short-term research will first focus on revisions of previously described species, the description of any new species and reducing the gaps in the largely unsampled areas in the interior of the country. Long-term research will focus on gaining detailed biological and ecological data. Here a brief report is presented on the progress of the project thus far, and what still needs to be achieved.

COLLOQUIUM: BEST STUDENT PAPER

Scytodes (Araneae: Scytodidae) spitting spiders of Southern Africa

R. Booysen & C. Haddad

Spitting spiders (Araneae, Scytodidae) are a very diverse group of haplogyne spiders, with four genera containing 240 species recorded worldwide. The largest genus, *Scytodes*, is represented by 219 species, and 35 of those are recorded from southern Africa. These descriptions were done by early naturalists and no revision for the southern African fauna exists. This project aims to address this issue by assessing the true diversity of *Scytodes* in southern Africa and establishing a morphological and genetic foundation for future research. To date, 155 morphospecies have been identified from various collections and fieldwork trips, and 123 of them are new to science. A new record for South Africa, *Scytodes univittata*, has been identified from the KwaZulu-Natal, Mpumalanga, Free State, and Gauteng provinces. Additionally, one record of the cosmopolitan species *S. fusca* has been recorded in South Africa, but the presence of *S. thoracica* is yet to be confirmed. Morphological examination is underway to describe each species and score physical characteristics for cladistic analysis. Genetic analyses will be performed using the mitochondrial gene regions COI and 18S, and the protein-coding gene region H3. *Scytodes caffra* from South Africa may potentially be a sub-social species, and its behaviour should be more comprehensively investigated.

COLLOQUIUM AWARDS

COLLOQUIUM: BEST POSTER

The spider type specimens deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida
M.M. Manyatsa, P. Marais, A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman & R. Lyle

The National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) was established in 1976 by the Agricultural Research Council – Plant Health and Protection (ARC-PHP) in Pretoria, South Africa. The collection forms part of South Africa’s Agricultural National Public Good Assets that the ARC manages. The curators of the NCA are not only responsible for the curation, preservation and management of specimens in collections but also for the type specimens. According to recommendation 72F, article 72 of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature, there are some obligations attributed to the institution in which type specimens are deposited, namely”...(1) ensure that all type specimens are clearly marked so that they will be unmistakably recognized as name-bearing types; (2) take all necessary steps for their safe preservation; (3) make them accessible for study; (4) publish lists of name-bearing types in its possession and; (5) so far as possible, communicate information concerning name-bearing types when requested. A summary of the types and associated data are provided. The spider type specimen collection of the NCA currently contains 2930 type specimens of 382 species, 256 genera and 39 families. Of these 302 specimens are primary holotypes.

NEW AFRAS COMMITTEE

Dr Tharina Bird
Chairman

Robin Lyle
Secretary

SANSA WELCOME DR. CASWELL MUNYAI

Dr. Caswell Munyai was the first PhD student of Stefan Foord and they have worked very closely on several projects throughout the years. Caswell attended the 14th Colloquium, and he told the delegates at the colloquium that he planned to continue with the research of Stefan.

Dr. Caswell Munyai is a Senior Lecturer teaching and researching on invertebrate biology and an NRF-rated scientist with almost a decade of experience in teaching and research in the discipline. He has published various peer-reviewed research articles both in national and international journals and has presented over 90 papers in both local and international conferences. Dr. Munyai has successfully supervised (to completion) eleven Honours, fifteen MSc and two PhD students between 2016 and 2021. His lab conducts research in various invertebrate biology topics including community ecology, the impacts of alien invasive plants, and their biological control. Most of his students are now documenting biodiversity response to land-use change and related effects across South Africa.

CASWELL WITH SOME OF HIS STUDENTS AND OTHER DELEGATES

Eugene Madiseng (ARC); Dr Caswell Munyai (Univ KZN); Grace Kioko (Nat. Mus. Kenya); Caroline Kunene (Univ. KZN); Asande Hadebe (Univ. KZN); Maggie Manyatsa (ARC); back: Thembile Khoza (SANBI); Dr Inam Yekwayo (Walter Sisulu Univ).

Group photo: 14th AFRAS COLLOQUIUM

NEW PUBLICATIONS

HADDAD C.R. & LYLE R. 2024. Three new genera of arboreal dark sac spiders from southern Africa (Araneae: Trachelidae). *Zootaxa* 5399(5): 451–504. doi:10.11646/zootaxa.5399.5.1

ABSTRACT: As part of a revision of the Afrotropical species of *Trachelas* L. Koch, 1872 (Araneae: Trachelidae), we distinguished three new genera of primarily arboreal spiders from southern Africa that are described here: *Coronarachne* gen. nov., represented by four new species known from both sexes, *C. denticulata* sp. nov. (type species), *C. penicillus* sp. nov., *C. setosa* sp. nov. and *C. unigena* sp. nov., and *C. neethlingi* sp. nov., known only from the male; *Falcaranea* gen. nov., represented by three new species known from both sexes, *F. amatola* sp. nov., *F. gladius* sp. nov. (type species) and *F. maputensis* sp. nov.; and *Trachecymbius* gen. nov., represented by five new species, *T. bosselaersi* sp. nov. (f), *T. felis* sp. nov. (m,f), *T. peterwebbi* sp. nov. (m), *T. tyume* sp. nov. (type species, f,m), and *T. umbella* sp. nov. (f). These three genera share the presence of strongly protruding setal bases on the ventral surfaces of the anterior legs, which are more strongly developed in males and can be mistaken for small ventral cusps that are found in several trachelid genera. Identification keys are provided for each of the three genera and their phylogenetic affinities to other Afrotropical Trachelidae are evaluated based on the cytochrome oxidase c subunit I (COI) gene. Most of the species described here were common in canopy fogging samples, and to a lesser extent beating, but are clearly a prominent component of the arboreal trachelid fauna in savanna and forest habitats in southern Africa.

Key words: Afrotropical, canopy fogging, cytochrome oxidase c subunit I, DNA barcoding, *Trachelas*.

Falcaranea gladius Photo: Peter Webb

Falcaranea gladius Photo: Ruan Booysen

NEW SOUTH AFRICAN SPECIES

Coronarachne denticulata Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Coronarachne penicillus Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Coronarachne setosa Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Coronarachne unigena Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Coronarachne neethlingi Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Falcaranea amatola Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Falcaranea gladius Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Falcaranea maputensis Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Trachecymbius bosselaersi Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Trachecymbius felis Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Trachecymbius peterwebbi Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Trachecymbius tyume Haddad & Lyle, 2024
Trachecymbius umbella Haddad & Lyle, 2024

Coronarachne denticulata Photo: Peter Webb

LATEST ON THE NEPHILIDS

HORMIGA G., KULKARNI S., ARNEDO M. A., DIMITROV D., GIRIBET G., KALLAL R. J. & SCHARFF N. 2023. Genitalic morphology and phylogenomic placement of the Australian spider *Paraplectanoides crassipes* Keyserling, 1886 (Araneae, Araneidae) with a discussion on the classification of the family Araneidae. *Invertebrate Systematics* 37(12): 797-818. doi:10.1071/IS23050

Subfamily **NEPHILINAE** Simon, 1894,
rank resurrected

Type: *Nephila* Leach, 1815.

Type species: *Aranea pilipes* Fabricius, 1793.

Nephilinae Simon, 1894. Dimitrov *et al.* (2017), Scharff *et al.* (2020), Kallal *et al.* (2020).

Nephilidae Simon, 1894. Kuntner (2006), Kuntner *et al.* (2019, 2023).

Composition

The Nephilinae clade includes the genera *Nephila* Leach, 1815; *Trichonephila* Dahl, 1911; *Clitaetra* Simon, 1889; *Indoetra* Kuntner, 2006; *Herennia* Thorell, 1877; *Nephilengys* L. Koch, 1872; and *Nephilingis* Kuntner, 2013.

NEW PUBLICATION

Wesołowska W. 2024. Taxonomic notes on the genus *Heliophanus* C.L. Koch, 1833, with description of three additional genera (Araneae: Salticidae: Chrysilini). *Zootaxa* 5405 (1): 80-92. doi:10.11646/zootaxa.5405.1.3

ABSTRACT: *Heliophanus* C.L. Koch, 1833 is a widespread genus of the family Salticidae, containing 170 nominal species (WSC 2023). Members of this genus are distributed in Palearctic, Oriental and Afrotropical Regions. Two species have also recently been introduced to the New World; *H. kochii* Simon, 1868 in northeastern USA (Gall & Edwards 2016) and *H. hamifer* Simon, 1886 in Brazil (Michelotto & Santos 2023). Simon (1901) proposed dividing this genus into three sections based on the position of the male palp apophyses. Wesołowska (1986) designated these sections as three subgenera in the revision of *Heliophanus*: *Heliophanus*, *Helafricanus* and *Heliocapensis*. And the genus *Trapezocephalus* Berland & Millot, 1941 was synonymized with *Heliophanus* to include the so-called orchestra group of species in *Heliophanus* sensu stricto (Wesołowska 1986). After almost 40 years, many new species of this genus have been described. Therefore, a reclassification of *Heliophanus* sensu lato is needed to deal with the dramatically increased species and morphological diversity, and incorporate the updated distributional data of this jumping spider genus. This paper aims to present a new classification for *Heliophanus* sensu lato, which comprises four genera: *Helafricanus*, *Heliocapensis*, *Heliophanus* s. str. and *Trapezocephalus*. These genera are redefined, their updated diagnoses and compositions are presented.

GENUS HELAFRICANUS Wesołowska, 1986

Spiders are small to medium sized, measuring 3–5.5 mm. The carapace is black, in some species with a thin whitish median streak. The abdomen in males is black, usually with a leaf-like pattern, or with a white median streak, sometimes also with a thin white line along the lateral edges of the body; in females with a light central stripe composed of several pairs of merging spots. Exceptionally males have abdominal pattern similar to females (e.g. *H. demonstrativus*). Light streaks/patches are composed of white hair.

Helafricanus bisulcus (Wesołowska, 1986)
Helafricanus debilis (Simon, 1901)
Helafricanus demonstrativus (Wesołowska, 1986)
Helafricanus fasciatus (Wesołowska, 1986)
Helafricanus hastatus (Wesołowska, 1986)
Helafricanus insperatus (Wesołowska, 1986)
Helafricanus marshalli (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)
Helafricanus modicus (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)
Helafricanus nanus (Wesołowska, 2003)
Helafricanus patellaris (Simon, 1901)
Helafricanus pauper (Wesołowska, 1986)
Helafricanus pistaciae (Wesołowska, 2003)
Helafricanus prozyskii (Wesołowska, 2003)
Helafricanus trepidus (Simon, 1910)

Peter Webb

GENUS HELIOCAPENSIS Wesołowska, 1986

Small spiders, ranging 3–4.5 mm, black colored, abdomen has a thin white line along anterior margin and two or three pairs of small round/diagonal white spots. These spots are composed of white hairs or small scales and spiders lose them as they live

Heliocapensis aberdarensis (Wesołowska, 1986)
Heliocapensis bellus (Wesołowska, 1986)
Heliocapensis capensis (Wesołowska, 1986)
Heliocapensis charlesi (Wesołowska, 2003)
Heliocapensis claviger (Simon, 1901)
Heliocapensis deserticola (Simon, 1901)
Heliocapensis mirabilis (Wesołowska, 1986)
Heliocapensis portentosus (Wesołowska, 1986)
Heliocapensis redimitus (Simon, 1910)
Heliocapensis termitophagus (Wesołowska & Haddad, 2002)

Peter Webb

GENUS HELIOPHANUS C.L. Koch, 1833

Heliophanus africanus Wesołowska, 1986
Heliophanus designatus Peckham & Peckham, 1903
Heliophanus gramineus Wesołowska & Haddad, 2013
Heliophanus hamifer Simon, 1886
Heliophanus horrifera Wesołowska, 1986
Heliophanus pratti Peckham & Peckham, 1903
Heliophanus pygmaeus Wesołowska & Russell-Smith, 2000
Heliophanus sororius Wesołowska, 2003

GENUS TRAPEZOCEPHALUS Berland & Millot, 1941

Medium sized spiders, ranging 4.5–7 mm, stocky body, uniformly black colored, in some species along the front edge of the abdomen there is a white narrow strip extending partly to the spides. Female epigyne with a scapus.

Trapezocephalus capicola (Simon, 1901)
Trapezocephalus deamatus (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)
Trapezocephalus infaustus (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)
Trapezocephalus lesserti (Wesołowska, 1986)
Trapezocephalus ndumoensis (Haddad & Wesołowska, 2013)
Trapezocephalus orchestra (Simon, 1885)
Trapezocephalus transvaalicus (Simon, 1901)

Peter Webb

NEW FAMILY FOR SOUTH AFRICA: MACROBUNIDAE

GORNEAU J.A., CREWS S.C., CALA-RIQUELME F., MONTANA K.O., SPAGNA J.C., BALLARIN F., ALMEIDA-SILVA L.M. & ESPOSITO L. A. 2023. Webs of intrigue: museum genomics elucidate relationships of the marronoid spider clade (Araneae). *Insect Systematics and Diversity* 7(5, 5): 1–18. doi:10.1093/isd/ixad021

ABSTRACT : Relationships among spider families that lack support through other lines of evidence (e.g., morphology) have recently been uncovered through molecular phylogenetics. One such group is the “marronoid” clade, which contains about 3,400 described species in 9 families. Marronoids run the gamut of life history strategies, with social species, species producing a variety of silk types, and species occurring in a range of extreme environments. Despite recognition of the ecological variability in the group, there remains uncertainty about family-level relationships, leaving diverse ecologies without an evolutionary context. The phylogenies produced to date have relatively low nodal support, there are few defined morphological synapomorphies, and the internal relationships of many families remain unclear. We use 93 exemplars from all marronoid families and ultraconserved element loci captured in silico from a combination of 48 novel low-coverage whole genomes and genomic data from the Sequence Read Archive (SRA) to produce a 50% occupancy matrix of 1,277 loci from a set of ultraconserved element probes. These loci were used to infer a phylogeny of the marronoid clade and to evaluate the familial relationships within the clade, and were combined with single-locus (Sanger) legacy data to further increase taxonomic sampling. Our results indicate a clearly defined and well-supported marronoid clade and provide evidence for both monophyly and paraphyly within the currently defined families of the clade. We propose taxonomic changes in accordance with the resulting phylogenetic hypothesis, including elevating Cicurinidae (restored status) and Macro bunidae (new rank).

Key words: low-coverage whole genome sequencing, phylogenetics, Cicurinidae, Macro bunidae, ultraconserved element.

The “marronoid” clade, is a group coined by Wheeler *et al.* (2017) from the Spanish word for brown (marrón), a reference to the fact that an overwhelming number of species in the clade are brown and generally morphologically nondescript. This moniker also serves as a statement to how little attention this group has received historically—brown is the most appropriate identifier.

Chresiona sp. found on plants Photo: Peter Webb

MACROBUNIDAE (new rank)

Chresiona convexa Simon, 1903
Chresiona invalida (Simon, 1898)
Chresiona nigrosignata Simon, 1903
Chumma bicolor Jocqué & Alderweireldt, 2018
Chumma foliata Jocqué & Alderweireldt, 2018
Chumma gastroperforata Jocqué, 2001
Chumma inquieta Jocqué, 2001
Chumma interfluvialis Jocqué & Alderweireldt, 2018
Chumma striata Jocqué & Alderweireldt, 2018
Chumma subridens Jocqué & Alderweireldt, 2018
Chumma tsitsikamma Jocqué & Alderweireldt, 2018
Macro bunus caffer (Simon, 1898)
Obatala armata Lehtinen, 1967
Pseudoauximus annulatus Purcell, 1908
Pseudoauximus pallidus Purcell, 1903
Pseudoauximus reticulatus Simon, 1902

Chresiona invalida Photo: Peter Webb

Chumma inquieta Photo: Jeremy Miller

Pseudoauximus sp. female Photo: Ruan Booysen

NEW PUBLICATION

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2024. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) of the South African Cape Floristic Kingdom. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa*, DOI: 10.1080/0035919X.2024.2324912

Spider species distribution in the Cape Floristic Kingdom (CFK) was compiled as part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), whose main aim was to create a relational database for the country's arachnid fauna. Data from the CFK was extracted from taxonomic and faunistic published papers, as well as unpublished faunistic survey data in national collections. A total of 11 500 records from 130 localities were recorded in the CFK until the end of 2023, representing 62 families, 334 genera and 960 species, with two further families (Synotaxidae and Theridiosomatidae) only known from undescribed species. This represents 42.4% of the total spider fauna of South Africa. For each species, the global and CFK distribution, as well as the level of endemism and a conservation assessment using the IUCN Red List criteria, are provided. A total of 269 spp. (28.0%) are endemic to the CFK, 49 spp. (5.1%) are of special concern, and 229 spp. (23.9%) are Data Deficient. However, most of the species (682 spp., 71.0%) have a wide distribution with no known threats and are categorised as Least Concern. Salticidae is the most species-rich family (128 spp.), with 30 spp. endemic to the CFK, followed by the Gnaphosidae (107 spp.), Thomisidae (86 spp.) and Lycosidae (49 spp.), while six families are represented by a single species. The last decade has seen an exponential growth in the knowledge of spiders in South Africa, and there are certainly many more species that must still be discovered and described.

Keywords: abundance; conservation status; endemism; Fynbos Biome; global distribution; South African National Survey of Arachnida.

Representative hunting spiders of the Cape Floristic Kingdom. A. *Chumma gastroperforata* (Amaurobiidae) (Photo: Ruan Booysen); P. *Harpactira cafreriana* (Theraphosidae) (Photo: Charles Haddad).

Extent of the Cape Floristic Region in southwestern South Africa, with the main protected areas (excluding the West Coast) indicated.

BOSELAERS J. 2024. A revision of the genus *Coryssiphus* Simon, 1903, with its transfer to Systariinae (Araneae: Miturgidae). *Zootaxa* 5415(1): 153–168. doi:10.11646/zootaxa.5415.1.7

ABSTRACT: The genus *Coryssiphus* Simon, 1903 is redescribed and found to be composed of two species. *Coryssiphus unicolor* Simon, 1903 is synonymised with *C. cinerascens* Simon, 1903, being the female of that species. *Coryssiphus praeustus* Simon, 1903 and *C. cinerascens* are redescribed and the genus is transferred from Liocranidae to Miturgidae: Systariinae based on a number of somatic and genitalic characters. The peculiar presence of *Coryssiphus* in Africa is briefly discussed.

Key words: Arachnida, Liocranidae, Cape Peninsula, spider, taxonomy

Coryssiphus praeustus Simon, 1903

Western Cape: Table Mountain; Kirstenbosch Botanical Gardens; Houtbaai, Tierbos; Skeleton Gorge Forest; Table Mountain, Orange Kloof Nature Reserve.

Coryssiphus cinerascens Simon, 1903

Western Cape: Cape Peninsula, Constantia; Vlakkenberg; Houtbaai, Tierbos; Kirstenbosch Botanical Gardens; Western slope of Table Mountain; Stellenbosch, Jonkershoek Nature Reserve.

Eye pattern

Setae on front legs

Coryssiphus cinerascens

WHICH ONE IS THE REAL *THOMISUS GHESQUIEREI* ?

Tommy Andriollo, a bat specialist was doing volunteering work in Western Uganda at a primate research station in Bugoma, last year (2022-2023), and he photographed a few spiders. He was unfortunately not able to collect specimens. He photographed this white *Thomisus* spider and compared it to the original drawings of Lessert (1943) of *Thomisus ghesquierei* that was originally described from Uganda.

However, when comparing it with the specimens from South Africa that was identified by Dippenaar-Schoeman (2023) as *Thomisus ghesquierei* it differs in colour. This might only be a colour variations, but it could also be a different species. He is presently trying to locate the type specimen.

REFERENCES

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LESSERT R. DE 1943. Araignées du Congo belge (Troisième partie). *Revue Suisse de Zoologie* 50(3): 305–338.

Tommy Andriollo

Drawing of Lessert (1943)

Peter Webb

Linda Wiese

Thomisus specimens from South Africa

SOME OBSERVATIONS

HAVE ANYBODY SEEN THIS SPIDER IN SOUTH AFRICA?

Tommy Andriollo, while volunteering in Western Uganda last year (2022-2023), also found this very interesting spider on bark. We were able to identify it for him as the flat crab spider *Heterogriffus berlandi* (Lessert, 1938). Unfortunately, he was not able to collect specimens but back in Europe he is investigating further and hopes to publish his results soon.

The species are presently known from Uganda, the Democratic Republic of the Congo and Angola. If anybody has seen them in South Africa please contact us. Dippenaaransie@gmail.com

The flat crab spider *Heterogriffus berlandi*

THE PINK LADY FROM THE FREE STATE

Allen Jones at the Mpetsane Conservation Estate (MCE) which is situated in the Eastern Free State highlands, some 14 km from Clocolan has already reported on several interesting orb-web spiders from the Free State grassland. He co-authored several papers on the garden orb-web spiders and the following three species *Argiope aurocincta*, *A. australis* and *A. lobata* have been reported from MCE. Several colour variations were reported on in *A. australis* including a "pink" variant. In January 2024 he again observed several of them in MCE. We are still not sure whether it is only a colour variant or maybe a different species.

Allen Jones at allenjones@lantic.net
SANSA team member Free State.

SOME MORE SPIDERS ID'S TO BE CONFIRMED

ZYGIELLA?

Linda Wiese

ACANTHEPEIRA?

Peter Webb

Drawings by Simon of type specimen

LARINIOIDES?

Allen Jones

MOLINARANEA ?

Jolandie Buck

Linda Wiese

Isoxya sp. From Stormsriver

ISOXYA SEMIFLAVA?

SOUTHERN AFRICA—RECENT PUBLICATIONS

AZARKINA G.N. & FOORD S.H. 2023. Further notes on the Afrotropical genus *Festucula* Simon, 1901 (Araneae, Salticidae). *ZooKeys* 1185: 285–308. doi: [org/10.3897/zookeys.1185.110365](https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.1185.110365)

BOSSELAERS J. 2024. A revision of the genus *Coryssiphus* Simon, 1903, with its transfer to Systariinae (Araneae: Miturgidae). *Zootaxa* 5415(1): 153–168. doi:10.11646/zootaxa.5415.1.7

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H. & LOTZ L.N. 2024. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) of the South African Cape Floristic Kingdom. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa*. DOI: 10.1080/0035919X.2024.2324912*

* This paper is dedicated to the memory of our late colleague and co-author, Stefan Foord, whose incredible contribution to the success of SANSA as an ecologist, data analyst and taxonomist will be sorely missed in the years to come.

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., LE ROUX E., ROUX C. & LOTZ L. 2023. A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden, South Africa. *SANSA Newsletter* 48 (December): 20–29. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10258744>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. & LOTZ L. 2023. Final report on the diversity of the Mountain Zebra National Park, South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae). *SANSA Newsletter* 48 (December): 30–37. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10275578>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. First record of the crab spider *Thomisus ghesquierei* Lessert, 1943 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 48 (December): 9–11. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10276180>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R. & WEBB P. 2023. More on the green lynx spider *Peucetia viridis* (Blackwall, 1858) in South Africa (Araneae: Oxyopidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 48 (December): 16–19. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10276831>

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. The male of *Thomisus kalaharinus* Lawrence, 1936 (Araneae, Thomisidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 48 (December): 12–15. [//doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10276936](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10276936).

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S. 2023. *Cheiracanthium furculatum* a formidable African spider. Please be aware of their presence in your house!! *SANSA Newsletter* 48 (December): 38–39.

GORNEAU J. A., CREWS S.C., CALA-RIQUELME F., MONTANA K.O., SPAGNA J.C., BALLARIN F., ALMEIDA-SILVA L. M. & ESPOSITO L. A. 2023. Webs of intrigue: museum genomics elucidate relationships of the marronoid spider clade (Araneae). *Insect Systematics and Diversity* 7(5, 5): 1–18. doi:10.1093/isd/ixad021

HADDAD C.R. & LYLE R. 2024. Three new genera of arboreal dark sac spiders from southern Africa (Araneae: Trachelidae). *Zootaxa* 5399(5): 451–504. doi:10.11646/zootaxa.5399.5.1

HORMIGA G., KULKARNI S., ARNEDO M. A., DIMITROV D., GIRIBET G., KALLAL R. J. & SCHARFF N. 2023. Genitalic morphology and phylogenomic placement of the Australian spier *Paraplectanoides crasipes* Keyserling, 1886 (Araneae, Araneidae) with a discussion on the classification of the family Araneidae. *Invertebrate Systematics* 37(12): 797–818. doi:10.1071/IS23050

SEBATA S., HADDAD C.R., FITZPATRICK M.J. & FOORD S.H., 2023. Spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) of a wildlife and cattle savanna ranch in South-Western Zimbabwe. *Koedoe* 65(1), a1756. <https://doi.org/10.4102/koedoe.v65i1.175>

WESOŁOWSKA W. 2024. Taxonomic notes on the genus *Heliophanus* C.L. Koch, 1833, with description of three additional genera (Araneae: Salticidae: Chrysellini). *Zootaxa* 5405 (1): 80–92. doi:10.11646/zootaxa.5405.1.3

NEWS FLASHES

CAMEL SPIDER WEBSITE

Paula Cushing like to advertise the fact that her lab has now revised and updated the camel spider website initiated by Warren Savary. The updated version can be found at: (<https://solifugae.org/>).

EUROPEAN CONGRESS OF ARACHNOLOGY

The **second circular** for 2024 European Congress of Arachnology is now available It will be held in Rennes in France from 25th to 30th August 2024. Please see european-arachnology.org or contact Julien directly on julien.petillon@univ-rennes.fr.

INTERNATIONAL SOCIETY OF ARACHNIDA NOW HAS OVER A THOUSAND MEMBERS!

For the first time in the history the International Society of Arachnology (ISA) now has more than 1000 members from across the world. This indicates a healthy interest in arachnids and the society and represents a very positive development for the future of arachnology.

VII LATIN AMERICAN CONGRESS OF ARACHNOLOGY
16–21 JUNE 2024
IN-PERSON AND VIRTUAL
BOGOTÁ, D.C.

We received the sad news about the death of the Canadian arachnologist, Charles Dondale, that passed away on 24th March in Ottawa, at the age of 96. He extensively published on the systematics of North American spiders. He visited the NCA collection in the late eighties and we was fortunate to host him.

Abdominal colour patterns of the sand diving spider *Ammoxenus amphalodes* (Araneae: Gnaphosidae) from South Africa

Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman¹, Tharina Bird² & Peter Webb†³

¹Project manager SANSA, South Africa. ²General Entomology, Ditsong National Museum of Natural History, Pretoria, South Africa. ³SANSA team member, deceased.

Abstract: The two types of abdominal patterns found in *Ammoxenus* species are discussed, with emphasis on *A. amphalodes* Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980. With images of live specimens, the two patterns are shown. Within the genus, there is large interspecific similarity, but intraspecific variability regarding the abdominal colour pattern. Due to these variations found species are sometimes wrongly identified.
Keywords: digging spines, harvester termites, monophagous predators, South African National Survey (SANSA).

INTRODUCTION

Presently six *Ammoxenus* species are listed in the World Spider Catalog (2024) all known only from Southern Africa. In the revision of the genus Benoit (1972) recognized five species, with Dippenaar & Meyer (1980) synonymizing one species and adding two new species but several new species have been identified (Bird, 2003).

They are well-studied monophagous specialist predators of harvester termites (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1996a, b; Haddad *et al.*, 2016; Petráková *et al.*, 2015). Extremely fast, these spiders move rapidly between foraging termites and even enter termite nest tunnels. They select a termite, kill it, and then drag it into loose sand, submerging themselves before eating their prey (Fig. 9). When disturbed, they dive head-first into the sand (Figs 16, 17) using special digging spines on the chelicerae (Fig. 15). They also bury their cup-like egg sacs. They are univoltine species with a wide reproductive period corresponding to the seasonal occurrence of termites. Large data sets were available from the South African National Survey (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) and they are easily sampled with pitfall traps.

In *Ammoxenus* species the abdominal pattern varies and in this paper, we look at the two types of abdominal patterns found with emphasis on *A. amphalodes* Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980. Due to these two patterns, species are sometimes wrongly identified.

RESULTS

Benoit (1972) illustrated the two main abdominal patterns (Figs 1, 2). In Fig. 1 the abdomen is uniformly covered with either dark brown or reddish brown iridescent setae. We refer to this as the 'glossy pattern' (Figs 3, 4) after Bird (2003). In Fig. 2 the pattern variations form a gradient, or intermediate pattern, between these two main patterns and here refer to as the dull pattern (Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980; Bird, 2003).

Figures 1–2. Images of two abdominal patterns after Benoit (1972).

Figures 3–5. *Ammoxenus amphalodes*. 3. Female dorsal view with glossy pattern. 4. Male dorsal view with glossy pattern. 5. Female with dull pattern. Photos: Peter Webb.

Figures 6–10. *Ammoxenus amphalodes*. 6. Line drawing of abdomen after Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980. 7. Female abdomen with dull pattern. 8. Female abdomen with glossy pattern. 9. Epigyne. 10. Female with dull pattern feeding on a termite. Photos: 7-9. Peter Webb. 10. Marie de Jager.

With the description of the female *A. amphalodes* the remarkable interspecific similarity in general appearance was recognized with only the genitalia that differs (Fig. 9). There is a wide range of variation within certain characteristics such as the position of the eyes, colour patterns on abdomen and width of clypeus. But it was especially the dorsal abdominal pattern that varies between specimens from dull (Figs 6, 7) to glossy (Figs 4, 5, 8). In *A. amphalodes* the abdomen of dull pattern individuals has no iridescent hairs, but a clear chevron pattern on the dorsal abdomen (Figs 6, 7). Great variation (intermediates) exists between these two main patterns, with varying degrees of the chevron pattern (Figs 12–14). In the glossy pattern the abdomen is decorated with two dark broad mediolateral bands. The only other marking is a cream band running anteriorly-posteriorly along the middle of the abdomen, often ending in a white, rounded area above the spinnerets, especially in the males (Fig. 5). The cream median band continues onto the cephalothorax (Fig. 11).

The reason for this colour variations is not clear. There seem to be indications for this pattern to be linked to distribution, but with exceptions nearly always present when the sample is large enough. For example, the dull pattern was found in about 70% of approximately 200 specimens of *A. psammodromus* Simon, 1910 collected in Dendron, Limpopo Province, South Africa (23°22'S, 29°23'E) while glossy but typical male and female patterns respectively were found in approximately 90 specimens of the same species collected at Florisbad, Free State Province, South Africa (28°46'S, 26°05'E).

The third author sampled and photographed specimens of *A. amphalodes* from a grassland near Irene for seven years (2013–2019). Males were observed from August to November (Figs 4, 16), glossy pattern females from October to March (Figs 3, 8, 11, 17), and dull pattern females from June to October (Figs 5, 7, 10, 12–14). Although the glossy pattern seems to fade to the dull pattern with time, this cannot account for all the dull pattern individuals as the same pattern is often found together within the same sample (Figs 12–14).

Figures 15–17. *Ammoxenus amphalodes*. 15. Chelicerae with digging spines. 16. Male diving. 17. Female diving. Photos: Peter Webb.

Figures 11–14. *Ammoxenus amphalodes*. Showing the variation in abdominal pattern. Photos: Peter Webb.

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Quick keys to the Bominae genera of South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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ABSTRACT: In this paper, keys are provided to identify the genera *Avelis* Simon, 1895, *Holopelus* Simon, 1886, *Parabomis*, 1901 and *Thomisops* Karsch, 1879 in the field and from photographs. With their small and round bodies they resemble seeds and may easily be overlooked in the field. The latest information on their distribution and conservation status in South Africa is provided.

Keywords: *Avelis*, distribution, *Holopelus*, *Parabomis*, South African National Survey of Arachnida, *Thomisops*

INTRODUCTION

Members of the subfamily Bominae (Araneae: Thomisidae) are a unique group of thomisid genera characterized by their small, globular bodies and short, stout legs (Ono, 1988). Five of the nine Bominae genera are known from the Afrotropical Region and four have been recorded from South Africa: *Avelis* Simon, 1895 (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1986a), *Holopelus* Simon, 1886 (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1986b), *Thomisops* Karsch, 1879 (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1989) and *Parabomis* Kulczynski, 1901 (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord, 2020).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) many specimens from several localities in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) were sampled but members of Bominae are rare in collections. They are very small and may easily be overlooked in the field. With their small and round bodies, they resemble seeds and is mainly collected by sweeping and beating grass, low shrubs and trees and hand collecting. However, during recent surveys some species have also been sampled from fogging tree canopies.

In this paper keys are provided to identify the Bominae genera and species from South African the field and photographs. The position of the eyes and size play an important part in identifying them. The latest information on their distribution, lifestyle and conservation status in South Africa are provided.

KEY TO THE GENERA OF BOMINAE IN SOUTH AFRICA

1. Anterior median eyes very widely spaced; clypeus wide and sloping (Figs 5, 6)***Parabomis***
- Anterior median eyes not as widely spaced; clypeus not as wide2
2. Anterior median eyes closer to each other than to the anterior lateral eyes (Figs 1, 2); lack dense spinulose area on margin of chelicerae***Avelis***
- Anterior median eyes closer to anterior lateral eyes or evenly spaced; dense spinulose area (arrow) on margin of chelicerae present (Fig. 8)3
3. Anterior eye row strongly recurved; anterior median eyes smaller than anterior lateral eyes; clypeus sloping (Figs 7, 8).....***Thomisops***
- Anterior eye row very slightly recurve, almost straight; anterior median eyes not smaller than rest; clypeus not sloping (Figs 3, 4)***Holopelis***

Avelis eye pattern

Figures 1–2. *Avelis* Simon, 1895

Holopelus eye pattern

Figures 3–4. *Holopelus* Simon, 1886

Parabomis eye pattern

Figures 5–6. *Parabomis* Kulczynski, 1901

Thomisops eye pattern and chelicerae with dense setae

Figures 7–8. *Thomisops* Karsch, 1879

GENUS AVELIS SIMON, 1895

SPECIES: *Avelis hystriculus* Simon, 1895

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape, Free State, KwaZulu-Natal, Limpopo, North West, Western Cape Provinces (Fig. 9).

CONSERVATION STATUS: Least Concern (LC).

Figures 17–18. *Holopelis albibarbis*. 17. Epigyne. 18. Male. (After Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1986b).

SPECIES: *Holopelis almiae* Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1986

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape, Western Cape Provinces (Fig. 19).

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC.

Figures 9–13. *Avelis hystriculus*. 9. Map showing distribution. 10. Female (P. Webb). 11. Female (L. Wiese). 12. Epigyne. 13. Palp. (After Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1986a).

Figures 19–23. *Holopelis almiae*. 19. Map showing distribution. 20. Female (C. Roux). 21. Male (L. Wiese). 22. Epigyne. 23. Palp. (After Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1986b)

GENUS HOLOPELUS SIMON, 1886

KEY TO THE SPECIES OF SOUTHERN AFRICA (FEMALES)

1. Carapace yellowish brown sometimes with greenish tint, with diffuse median bands (Figs 15, 16). Abdomen ivory with scattered dark spots. Legs pale sometimes with femur distally with bands. Genitalia (Figs 17, 18).....*H. albibarbis*
- Carapace reddish brown with diffuse median bands (Fig. 20). Abdomen ivory with sigilla brown. Legs yellow brown. Genitalia (Figs 22, 23)*H. almiae*

SPECIES: *Holopelis albibarbis* Simon, 1895

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape, Northern Cape Western Cape Provinces (Fig. 14).

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC.

Figures 14–16. *Holopelis albibarbis*. 14. Map showing distribution. 15–16. Photos: 15. Sally Adams. 16. Jolandie Buck.

GENUS PARABOMIS Kulczyński, 1901

KEY TO THE SPECIES OF SOUTHERN AFRICA

1. Carapace with numerous club-shaped setae (Fig. 39).....*P. pilosus*
 — Carapace without dense club-shaped setae; retro tibial apophysis in male palp elongate or hook-like2
2. Carapace and legs strongly mottled; epigyne egg shaped (Fig. 26); retro tibial apophysis in male palp hooklike (Fig. 27) *P. elsaie*
 — Carapace and legs uniform; retro tibial apophyses long ..3
3. Retro tibial apophysis directed upwards (Fig. 36)
*P. megae*
 — Retro tibial apophysis extending sideways (Fig. 32).....
*P. martinae*

SPECIES: *Parabomis elsa* Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord, 2020

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Free State, Gauteng, Limpopo, KwaZulu-Natal, and Mpumalanga Provinces (Fig. 24).
CONSERVATION STATUS: LC.

Figures 24–27. *Parabomis elsa*. 24. Map showing distribution. 25. Female lateral view (Les Oates). 26. Epigyne 27. Palp. (After Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord, 2020).

SPECIES: *Parabomis martini* Lessert, 1919

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape, Free State, Gauteng, Limpopo, KwaZulu-Natal, Mpumalanga, North West, Northern Cape Provinces (Fig. 28).
CONSERVATION STATUS: LC.

Figures 28–32. *Parabomis martini*. 28. Map showing distribution. 29–30. Females from Eastern Cape. 31. Epigyne. 32. Palp. (After Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord, 2020).

SPECIES: *Parabomis megae* Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord,

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Limpopo Province (Fig. 33).
CONSERVATION STATUS: LC.

Figures 33–37. *Parabomis megae*. 33. Map showing distribution. 34. Female. 35. Male. 36. Epigyne. 37. Palp. (After Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord, 2020).

SPECIES: *Parabomis pilosus* Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord, 2020

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Limpopo Province (Fig. 38).
CONSERVATION STATUS: LC.

Figures 38–42. *Parabomis pilosus*. 38. Map showing distribution. 39–40. Female (John Wilkinson). 41. Epigyne. 42. Palp. (After Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord, 2020).

GENUS THOMISOPS

KEY TO THE SPECIES OF SOUTHERN AFRICA (FEMALES)

- 1. Abdomen roundish, wider than long **2**
- Abdomen rectangular, slightly longer than wide (Fig. 7) *T. lesserti*

- 2. Carapace and legs mottled and coarsely granulated (Fig. 54) *T. granulatus*
- Body and legs not granulated.....**3**

- 3. Femora of all the legs with a broad yellow band (Fig. 11) *T. sulcatus*
- Femora not banded**4**

- 4. Abdomen with circular patterns.....**5**
- Abdomen without patterns, only scattered black spots (Fig. 45)..... *T. bullatus*

- 5. Abdomen with very distinct circular pattern (Fig. 64) *T. pupa*
- Abdomen with faint circular pattern (Fig. 69)..... *T. senegalensis*

SPECIES: *Thomisops bullatus* Simon, 1895

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape, Gauteng, KwaZulu-Natal, Limpopo, Mpumalanga Provinces (Fig. 43).
CONSERVATION STATUS: LC.

Figures 43–48. *Thomisops bullatus*. 43. Map showing distribution. 44. Female (Bruce Blake). 45. Female (Wynand Uys). 46. Epigyne. 47. Palp. 48. Male habitus (After Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1989).

SPECIES: *Thomisops granulatus* Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1989

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape, KwaZulu-Natal Provinces (Fig. 49).
CONSERVATION STATUS: LC.

Figures 49–54. *Thomisops granulatus*. 49. Map showing distribution. 50–51. Female (Lynette Rudman). 52. Epigyne. 53. Palp. 54. Granulation (After Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1989).

SPECIES: *Thomisops lesserti* Millot, 1942

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape, KwaZulu-Natal, Gauteng Provinces (Fig. 55).
CONSERVATION STATUS: LC.

Figures 55–59. *Thomisops lesserti*. 55. Map showing distribution. 56–57. Female (Peter Webb). 58. Epigyne. 59. Palp. (After Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1989).

SPECIES: *Thomisops melanopes* Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1989

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA:

Eastern Cape; KwaZulu-Natal; Limpopo; Mpumalanga; North West; Western Cape Provinces (Fig. 60).

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC.

Figures 60–63. *Thomisops melanopes*. 60. Map showing distribution. 61–62. Male (Ernst Klimsa). 63. Male palp. (After Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1989)

SPECIES: *Thomisops pupa* Karsch, 1879

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA:

Eastern Cape; Gauteng, KwaZulu-Natal, North West; Limpopo; Mpumalanga Provinces (Fig. 63).

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC.

Figures 63–67. *Thomisops pupa*. 63. Map showing distribution. 64. Female (P. Webb). 65. Male. 66. Epigyne. 67. Palp. (After Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1989).

SPECIES: *Thomisops senegalensis* Millot, 42

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA:

Eastern Cape, Northern Cape; Western Cape; KwaZulu-Natal; Mpumalanga Provinces (Fig. 68).

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC.

Figures 68–72. *Thomisops senegalensis*. 68. Map showing distribution. 69. Female (P. Webb). 70. Female. 71. Epigyne. 72. Palp. (After Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1989)

SPECIES: *Thomisops sulcatus* Simon, 1895

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA:

Eastern Cape; Free State; Gauteng; KwaZulu-Natal; Limpopo; Mpumalanga; Western Cape Provinces (Fig. 73).

CONSERVATION STATUS: (LC).

Figures 73–77. *Thomisops sulcatus*. 73. Map showing distribution. 74. Female (P. Webb). 75. Male. 76. Epigyne. 77. Palp. (After Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1989)

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Records of *Artema atlanta* Walckenaer, 1837 from South Africa (Araneae: Pholcidae)

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ABSTRACT: Records of the spider *Artema atlanta* Walckenaer, 1837 from South Africa are presented. The general morphology of live specimens is discussed, and photographs are provided, with notes on their behaviour and distribution.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), synanthropic

INTRODUCTION

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) spiders were sampled throughout the country (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). The first record of *Artema atlanta* Walckenaer, 1837 from Pella in the Northern Cape was reported on in 2007 (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

The genus *Artema* Walckenaer, 1837 is known from 12 species but only *Artema atlanta* has been recorded from South Africa. This species has a pantropical distribution. It has been recorded throughout Africa and Madagascar and is recorded in six provinces in South Africa.

The objective of this paper is to discuss the behaviour, and provide all the distribution records of *A. atlanta* from South Africa.

DIAGNOSTIC CHARACTERS

Artema atlanta is easily distinguished from other pholcids by its large body and strong legs (body length 5.5–9.5 mm; leg span up to 15 cm) (Fig. 1) The colour is variable, even within species with the carapace pale to light brown, sometimes with brown radial marks (Fig. 2), with light to dark brown median band; clypeus with wide light brown band (Fig. 3). The abdomen is pale gray to light brown, usually with dark dots dorsally, arranged in distinctive stripes from the dorsal to lateral side of the abdomen (Figs 2, 3). Legs pale yellow to ochre with dark rings on femora subdistally, patellae + tibiae proximally, and tibiae subdistally, tips of femora and tibiae whitish. Carapace with median pit and distinct posterior furrow; ocular area slightly elevated (Fig. 2). Abdomen globose and high (Fig. 1). Legs without spines; with long curved hairs, especially on tibiae and metatarsi. Females in general like males, but their legs are shorter, and stridulatory files laterally on chelicerae are always present and distinct.

LIFESTYLE

The species lives in space-webs found in a variety of habitats that are usually shady and dark. The web is made of non-sticky silk and often appears irregular. They have been sampled from sheltered habitats such as caves, holes and crevices, and spaces under large rocks. *Artema atlanta* is an invasive species and it was also sampled from buildings in South Africa.

Figures 1–3. *Artema atlanta* female from Hoedspruit, Limpopo. 1. Lateral view. 2. Dorsal view. 3. Anterior view. Photos: Peter Webb.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Pantropical. In Africa, the species is introduced in several countries: Madagascar, Mozambique, St Helena, Sudan, Tanzania, Kenya, Uganda, Somalia, Guinea, Togo, Benin Namibia, Botswana

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Free State: Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22). **Gauteng:** Pretoria, Annlin (-25.679, 28.199). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Bluff (-29.88, 31.02). **Limpopo:** Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93); Luvhondo Mountain Retreat (-23.038, 29.442); Phalaborwa (-23.94, 31.14); Kammersrus(-24.48, 30.83). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park, Satara (-24.405, 31.766). **Northern Cape:** Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17); Augrabies National Park (-28.53, 20.29); Upington (-28.45, 21.24); Groblershoop (-28.88, 21.98); Pella (-29.03, 19.13).

Map 1. Showing the distribution of *Artema atlanta* Walckenaer, 1837 in South Africa

HABITAT

In 2006 for the first time *A. atlanta* was sampled in a remote village of Pella in the Northern Cape. In one cottage the walls and ceiling were draped in dusty webs inhabiting specimens (Leroy, 2007).

In 2012 the SANSA Spider Identification Service received a call from Hoedspruit in the Limpopo Province about a possible “violin spider” invasion of houses. In one house alone more than 200 specimens were sampled. The spiders were running around the houses over furniture causing a big scare as a result of being wrongly identified. Samples were sampled, identified as *A. atlanta* and photographed (Figs 1-3, 5).

In South Africa, it has also been and sampled from the Desert, Grassland, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Succulent Karoo biomes.

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Female from Hoedspruit, Limpopo Peter Webb

Female from Kammersrus, Limpopo Peter Webb

Female from Groblershoop, Northern Cape Ruan Booyesen

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LYLE R., LOTZ L.N. & MARAIS P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA): Review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70: 245–275.

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A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Garden Route National Park

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ABSTRACT: An annotated species list of spiders from the Garden Route National Park (GRNP) is provided. The checklist was compiled from data collected from the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) database. A total of 245 species from 52 families and 166 genera are presently protected in the park. The most species-rich families are the Thomisidae (34 spp.), Salticidae (28 spp.) and Araneidae (22 spp.), while 15 families are represented by singletons. The global distribution, endemism and conservation status for each species is provided. A large percentage (83.2%) of the species have a wide distribution range and are of Least Concern while 17 species are Data Deficient and 10 species are of special concern. Seven species are known only from the Garden Route National Park.

Keywords: conservation, endemism, fynbos, indigenous forests, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA).

INTRODUCTION

In terms of the National Environmental Management: Protected Areas Act, 2003 (Act No 57 of 2003), the primary mandate of SANParks is to oversee the conservation of South Africa’s biodiversity, landscapes and associated heritage assets through a system of national parks. In 1997 the Agricultural Research Council registered a project (DIPSA 1296) at SANParks, to determine the diversity of arachnids in the different parks.

One of the core research areas of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) is to determine the number of arachnid species presently conserved in protected areas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). The South African National Parks (SANParks) are key to South Africa’s conservation initiatives. Species distribution data generated through SANParks and other protected areas fed into the conservation assessments used to compile the Red Data List of the Arachnida of South Africa (Foord *et al.*, 2020).

The Garden Route National Park (GRNP), established by SANParks in 2009, spans 121 000 hectares and includes the old Wilderness and Tsitsikamma National Parks, the Knysna Lakes area, and roughly 52 000 hectares of newly proclaimed land (Fig. 1). The individual Parks have to retain their identity and become camps in the greater GRNP, known as Tsitsikamma and Wilderness. It forms part of the Garden Route Biosphere Reserve (GRBR) which was recognised by UNESCO as South Africa’s 9th Biosphere Reserve in June 2017.

The GRNP is regarded as a critical focus area. It is home to a section of 60 500 hectares of indigenous forest - the largest continuous complex of such forest in the country, and the fynbos of the Garden Route falls within the Cape Floristic region - a global diversity hotspot (Figs 1-4). The Garden Route National Park is an example of 'conservation without boundaries.' Over 1 000 private landowners border the park and a need to create a stewardship program that encourages these residents of the Garden Route to help conserve the natural heritage of the area. The park has a temperate climate in which rainfall occurs throughout the year.

MAP 1: Map showing location of the Garden Route National Park.

Figures 1–3. The Garden Route National Park different habitats. Photos: Linda Wiese.

Figure 4. The Tsitsikamma section is known for its indigenous forests, and uneven coastline. Photo: Linda Wiese.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Studie area: The Tsitsikamma section of the park covers an 80 kilometres long stretch of coastline with Nature's Valley at the western end of the park (Figs 2 & 4). The section is known for its indigenous forests and uneven coastline.

The Wilderness section is located around the seaside town of Wilderness in the Western Cape between the larger towns of George, Sedgefield and Knysna, in the Western Cape (Map 1). It stretches from the Touws River mouth to the Swartvlei estuary and beyond, where it links with the Goukamma Nature Reserve, giving protection to five lake areas. This section of the park protects three major zones of indigenous forest, four types of fynbos, plus various lakes and winding waterways.

Sampling methods and identification: Spiders were sampled during short surveys undertaken by the arachnologists of the National Museum, Bloemfontein (NMB) (second author) and ARC-National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) (first author) and a SANSA team member (third author) as well as some visiting scientists. Canopy fogging surveys were also undertaken by students at the University of Stellenbosch (Swart *et al.* 2020) and Garden Route National Park (Swart *et al.*, 2018, 2019, 2020a; Swart, Samways & Roets, 2020b). The specimens sampled are housed in the NCA and NMB museum collections in 70% ethanol.

Endemicity value (END): This value was determined based on the known distribution of each species: (6) only known from the type locality that could be in the Eastern Cape or Western Cape; (5) endemic to either the Eastern Cape (ECE) or Western Cape Provinces (WCE); (4) known from both provinces and an adjoining province; (3) endemic to South Africa (SAE); (2) endemic to southern Africa (STHE); (1) endemic to the Afrotropical Region (AE); (0) also recorded outside the Afrotropical Region (C).

Conservation status (CS): This value was determined for each species from a recent Red List assessment of spiders in South Africa. LC: least concern, when species has a wide distribution; DD: data deficient, through either a lack of distribution data or taxonomic resources; NE: not evaluated; VU: vulnerable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 52 families represented by 166 genera and 245 species have been collected from GRNP (Table 1; Appendix 1). In the First Atlas of South African Spiders (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010) 182 species were listed from the GRNP. Of the three National parks surveyed in the Western Cape the number of species collected in the GRNP is higher than the 116 species recorded from the Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999), and the 184 species from the Bontebok National Park

TABLE 1. Spider diversity of Garden Route National Park, with total number of families, genera (GEN) and species (SPP) sampled.

FAMILY	GEN	SPP.	FAMILY	GEN	SPP.
Amaurobiidae	1	6	Mysmenidae	1	1
Anapidae	1	1	Nephilidae	1	2
Araneidae	16	22	Oecobiidae	1	1
Archaeidae	1	1	Oonopidae	1	1
Caponiidae	1	2	Orsolobidae	1	1
Cheiracanthiidae	3	6	Oxyopidae	3	4
Clubionidae	1	2	Palpimanidae	1	2
Corinnidae	3	4	Philodromidae	3	3
Ctenidae	2	2	Pholcidae	2	3
Cyatholipidae	3	3	Phyxelididae	4	4
Cyrtoucheniidae	1	1	Pisauridae	4	5
Deinopidae	1	1	Salticidae	18	28
Desidae	2	2	Scytodidae	1	2
Dictynidae	2	2	Segestriidae	1	1
Drymusidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	6
Eresidae	1	1	Sicariidae	2	2
Gallieniellidae	1	2	Sparassidae	1	2
Gnaphosidae	4	11	Tetragnathidae	4	7
Hahniidae	1	3	Theraphosidae	2	3
Hersiliidae	2	2	Theridiidae	10	13
Linyphiidae	7	7	Thomisidae	21	34
Liocranidae	1	1	Trachelidae	6	6
Lycosidae	7	9	Trochanteriidae	1	1
Migidae	1	2	Uloboridae	3	3
Mimetidae	1	1	Zodariidae	5	6
Miturgidae	1	1	Zoropsidae	2	8

(Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021) and 261 species from the Table Mountain National Park (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, in press). In this survey, the Thomisidae (34 spp.), Salticidae (28 spp.) and Araneidae (22 spp.) were the most species-rich families (Table 1). There was 15 families represented by a single species.

Conservation status: Of the 245 species sampled, 23 spp. (9.4 %) are data deficient (DD), i.e. lacking taxonomic or distribution data, while 11 spp. (4.5 %) were not evaluated (NE), indicating possible new species or species only sampled from juveniles (Table 1; Appendix 1). The majority of the species (201 spp., 83.0 %) sampled are listed as being of least concern (LC), and ten species were of special concern.

TABLE 2: Conservation status and of the spider species sampled at the Garden Route National Park.

CONSERVATION STATUS	SPP.	%
Data deficient (DD)	23	9.4
Not evaluated (NE)	11	4.5
Least concern (LC)	201	82
Rare	4	1.6
Endangered	3	1.2
Vulnerable	2	0.8
Near Threatened	1	0.4

TABLE 3: Species of special concern in the Garden Route National Park. Conservation status (CON), Endemicity (END): RA = Rare; VUL = Vulnerable; NT = Near Threatened; ECE = Eastern Cape endemic; WCE = Western Cape endemic.

SPECIES	CON	END
AMAUROBIIDAE		
<i>Chumma striata</i> Jocqué & Alderweireldt, 2017	RA	WCE
<i>Chumma inquieta</i> Jocqué, 2001	EN	EC,WC
CYATHOLIPIDAE		
<i>Ilisoa knysna</i> Griswold, 1987 (Fig. 5)	VUL	WCE
DRYMUSIDAE		
<i>Izithunzi silvicola</i> (Purcell, 1904) (Fig. 6)	RA	EC,WC
MIGIDAE		
<i>Moggridgea intermedia</i> Hewitt, 1913	RA	WCE
PHOLCIDAE		
<i>Quamtana knysna</i> Huber, 2003 (Fig. 5)	EN	WCE
THOMISIDAE		
<i>Mystaria lindaicapensis</i> Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014 (Fig. 7)	VUL	EC,WC
<i>Simorcus haddadi</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2010 (Fig. 8)	NT	WCE
ZODARIIDAE		
<i>Diores silvestris</i> Jocqué, 1990	RARE	WCE
<i>Procydrela precursor</i> Jocqué, 1999	EN	EC,WC

Endemicity: Of the species identified to species level only 107 spp. (43.7%) are South African endemics; 27.8% are African endemics and 14.3% are Southern African endemics while 24 species has a distribution wider than Africa (Table 4; Appendix 1). Seven species are endemic to the GRNP and 28 species are Western Cape endemics.

TABLE 4. Endemicity of the spider species sampled at the Garden Route National Park.

ENDEMICITY	SPP.	%
0 – Africa and wider (C)	24	9.8
1 – African endemics (AE)	69	27.8
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	35	14.3
3 – SA endemics (SAE)	44	18
4 – SA (SAE): 2 adjacent provinces	28	11.4
5 – Eastern Cape endemics (ECE)	1	0.4
5 – Western Cape endemics (WCE)	27	11
6 –Known only from type locality	7	2.9

Figure 5. *Quamtana knysna* a vulnerable species. Photo: Linda Wiese.

Figure 6. *Izithunzi silvicola* a rare species. Photo David Wildeman.

Figure 7. *Mystaria lindaicapensis* a vulnerable species. Photo: Linda Wiese.

Figure 8. *Simorcus haddadi* a near threatened species. Photo: Charles Haddad.

Figures 9–23. Araneidae: 9. *Isoxya cf semiflava*. 10. *Gea infuscata*. 11. *Neoscona hirta*. 12. *Cyrtophora citricola*. 13. *Larinia chloris*. 14. *Caponia capensis* (Caponiidae). 15. *Cheiracanthium furculatum* (Cheiracantiidae). 16. *Badumna longinqua* (Desidae). 17. *Zelotes fuliginus* (Gnaphosidae). 18. *Hahnia tabulicola* (Hahniidae). 19. *Foveosa foveolata* (Lycosidae). 20. *Pardosa crassipalpis* (Lycosidae). 21. *Chiasmopes lineatus* (Pisauridae). 22. *Peucetia nicolae* (Oxyopidae). 23. *Oxyopes affinis* (Oxyopidae). Photos: Linda Wiese, except 13. Martie Rheeder.

Figures 24–38. 24. *Quamtana knysna* (Pholcidae). 25. *Baryphas ahenus* (Salticidae). 26. *Helaffricanus patellaris* (Salticidae). 27. *Thyene inflata* (Salticidae). 28. *Steatoda capensis* (Theridiidae). 29. *Theridula* sp. ? (Theridiidae). 30. *Leucauge festiva* (Tetragnathidae). 31. *Leucauge thomeensis* (Tetragnathidae). Thomisiidae: 32. *Phrynarachne melloleitaai*. 33. *Pherecydes tuberculatus*. 34. *Runcinia aethiops*. 35. *Synema nigrotibiale*. 36. *Tmarus cameliformis*. 37. *Thomisus scrupus*. 38. *Thomisus blandus*. Photos: Linda Wiese.

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APPENDIX 1: Spiders of Garden Route National Park listing their endemismy (END), conservation status (CON), country endemismy (CEND) and provincial endemismy (PROV). LC Least Concern, DD Data Deficient, VU Vulnerable, NE Not Evaluated, EN Endangered

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND	PROV
Anapidae	<i>Crozetulus rhodesiensis</i> Brignoli, 1981	2	LC	STHE	
Araneidae	<i>Arachnura scorpionoides</i> Vinson, 1863	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Caerostris sexcupidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Cyrtarachne ixoides</i> (Simon, 1870)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775) (Fig. 12)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C.L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Gea infusata</i> Tullgren, 1910 (Fig. 10)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Hypsosinga lithyphantoides</i> Caporiacco, 1947	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Ideocaira transversa</i> Simon, 1903	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Isoxya cicatricosa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Isoxya tabulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Larinia chloris</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Nemoscolus elongatus</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Neoscona hirta</i> (C. L. Koch, 1844) (Fig. 11)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Neoscona theisi theisiella</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	C	
	<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Paralarinia bartelsi</i> (Lessert, 1933)	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Paraplectana thornstoni</i> (Blackwall, 1865) (Fig. 9)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE	
<i>Trichonephila senegalensis annulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE		
Archaeidae	<i>Afrarchaea</i> sp. 1 (imm.)		NE		
Caponiidae	<i>Caponia capensis</i> Purcell, 1904	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Caponia forficifera</i> Purcell, 1904	5	DD	SAE	WCE
Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Cheiramiona ansiae</i> Lotz, 2003	4	LC	SAE	
	<i>Cheiramiona collinita</i> (Lawrence, 1938)	4	LC	SAE	
	<i>Cheiramiona plaatbosensis</i> Lotz, 2015	4	LC	SAE	WC,EC
	<i>Cheiramiona stellenboschiensis</i> Lotz, 2003	5	DD	SAE	WCE
	<i>Lessertina capensis</i> Haddad, 2014	5	DD	SAE	WCE
Clubionidae	<i>Clubiona abbajensis</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Clubiona biaculeata</i> Simon, 1897	3	DD	SAE	
Corinnidae	<i>Copuetta lacustris</i> (Strand, 1916)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Merenius alberti</i> Lessert, 1923	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Pronophaea natalica</i> Simon, 1897	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Pronophaea proxima</i> (Lessert, 1923)	3	LC	SAE	
Ctenidae	<i>Anahita</i> sp. 1 (imm.)		NE		
	<i>Ctenus parvoculatus</i> Benoit, 1979	3	LC	SAE	
Cyatholipidae	<i>Cyatholipus quadrimaculatus</i> Simon, 1894	4	LC	SAE	
	<i>Ilisoa knysna</i> Griswold, 1987	5	VU	SAE	WCE
	<i>Ulwembua outeniqua</i> Griswold, 1987	4	LC	SAE	WC,EC
Cyrtaucheniidae	<i>Ancylotrypa</i> sp. 1(imm.)		NE		
Deinopidae	<i>Menneus dromedarius</i> Purcell, 1904	1	LC	AE	
Desidae	<i>Badumna longinqua</i> (L. Koch, 1867)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Desis formidabilis</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1891)	2	LC	STHE	

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND	PROV	
Dictynidae	<i>Archaeodictyna</i> sp. 1		NE			
	<i>Mashimo leleupi</i> Lehtinen, 1967	1	LC	AE		
Drymusidae	<i>Izithunzi silvicola</i> (Purcell, 1904)	4	RARE	SAE	WC,EC	
Eresidae	<i>Gandanameno fumosa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	3	LC	SAE		
Gallieniellidae	<i>Drassodella aurostriata</i> Mbo & Haddad, 2019	5	LC	SAE	WCE	
	<i>Drassodella quinquelabecula</i> Tucker, 1923	5	LC	SAE	WCE	
Gnaphosidae	<i>Camillina biplagia</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE		
	<i>Ibala bilinearis</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE		
	<i>Xerophaeus matroosbergensis</i> Tucker, 1923	4	LC	SAE	WC,EC	
	<i>Xerophaeus rubeus</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE		
	<i>Xerophaeus tenebrosus</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE		
	<i>Zelotes broomi</i> (Purcell, 1907)	5	LC	SAE	WCE	
	<i>Zelotes fuligineus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE		
	<i>Zelotes invidus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE		
	<i>Zelotes kuncinyanus</i> FitzPatrick, 2007	6	DD	SAE	WCE	
	<i>Zelotes reduncus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE		
	<i>Zelotes scrutatus</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)	1	LC	AE		
	Hahniidae	<i>Hahnia clathrata</i> Simon, 1898	2	LC	STHE	
		<i>Hahnia tabulicola</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE	
<i>Hahnia zodarioides</i> (Simon, 1898)		3	LC	SAE		
Hersiliidae	<i>Hersilia setifrons</i> Lawrence, 1928	2	LC	STHE		
	<i>Neotama corticola</i> (Lawrence, 1937)	3	LC	SAE		
Linyphiidae	<i>Afribactrus styliifrons</i> Wunderlich, 1995	6	DD	SAE	WCE	
	<i>Agyneta habra</i> (Locket, 1968)	1	LC	AE		
	<i>Callitrichia gloriosa</i> (Jocqué, 1984)	5	LC	SAE	ECE	
	<i>Frontinellina locketi</i> van Helsdingen, 1970	3	LC	SAE		
	<i>Mecynidis dentipalpis</i> Simon, 1894	2	LC	STHE		
	<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE		
	<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1880)	0	LC	C		
Liocranidae	<i>Andromma raffrayi</i> Simon, 1899	3	DD	SAE		
Lycosidae	<i>Foveosa foveolata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	1	LC	AE		
	<i>Hippasa funerea</i> Lessert, 1925	2	LC	STHE		
	<i>Minicosa neptuna</i> Alderweireldt & Jocqué, 2007	3	LC	STHE		
	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE		
	<i>Proevippa biampliata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE		
	<i>Proevippa fascicularis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE		
	<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE		
	<i>Trabea rubriceps</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE		
	<i>Zenonina albocaudata</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE		
Macroibunidae	<i>Chresiona</i> sp. 1 (new?)		NE			
	<i>Chumma gastroperforata</i> Jocqué, 2001	4	LC	SAE	WC, EC	
	<i>Chumma inquieta</i> Jocqué, 2001	4	EN	SAE	EC, WC	
	<i>Chumma striata</i> Jocqué & Alderweireldt, 2018	5	RARE	SAE	WCE	
	<i>Chumma tsitsikamma</i> Jocqué & Alderweireldt, 2018	6	DD	SAE	ECE	
	<i>Obatala</i> sp. 1 (imm.)		NE			
Migidae	<i>Moggridgea intermedia</i> Hewitt, 1913	5	RARE	SAE	WCE	
	<i>Moggridgea peringueyi</i> Simon, 1903	3	LC	SAE		
Mimetidae	<i>Ero capensis</i> Simon, 1895	2	LC	STHE		
Miturgidae	<i>Parapostenus hewitti</i> Lessert, 1923	3	LC	SAE		
Mysmenidae	<i>Isela okuncana</i> Griswold, 1985	4	DD	SAE		

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND	PROV
Oecobiidae	<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	0	LC	C	
Oonopidae	<i>Australoonops granulatus</i> Hewitt, 1915	3	LC	SAE	
Orsolobidae	<i>Afrilobus australis</i> Griswold & Platnick, 1987	5	DD	SAE	WCE
Oxyopidae	<i>Hamataliwa fronticornis</i> (Lessert, 1927)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Oxyopes affinis</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Oxyopes flavipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Peucectia nicolae</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994	3	LC	SAE	
Palpimanidae	<i>Palpimanus capensis</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Palpimanus globulifer</i> Simon, 1893	3	DD	SAE	
Philodromidae	<i>Philodromus guineensis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	0	LC	C	
	<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	
Pholcidae	<i>Quamtana knysna</i> Huber, 2003	5	EN	SAE	WCE
	<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Smeringopus ubicki</i> Huber, 2012	4	LC	SAE	WC,EC
Phyxelididae	<i>Lamaika distincta</i> Griswold, 1990	6	DD	SAE	WCE
	<i>Matundua silvatica</i> (Purcell, 1904)	5	DD	SAE	WCE
	<i>Namaquarachne tropata</i> Griswold, 1990	5	LC	SAE	WCE
	<i>Vidole capensis</i> (Pocock, 1900)	3	LC	SAE	
Pisauridae	<i>Chiasmopes lineatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Euprosthénopsis pulchella</i> (Pocock, 1902)	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Nilus curtus</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Nilus massajae</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Rothus vittatus</i> Simon, 1898	3	LC	SAE	
Salticidae	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Euophrys cochlea</i> Wesolowska, Azarkina & Russell-Smith, 2014	5	LC	SAE	WCE
	<i>Euophrys miranda</i> Wesolowska, Azarkina & Russell-Smith, 2014	6	DD	SAE	ECE
	<i>Euophrys nana</i> Wesolowska, Azarkina & Russell-Smith, 2014	6	DD	SAE	WCE
	<i>Evarcha denticulata</i> Wesolowska & Haddad, 2013	4	LC	SAE	
	<i>Habrocestum luculentum</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	4	DD	SAE	
	<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Helafricanus debilis</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Helafricanus patellaris</i> (Simon, 1901)	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Heliocapensis claviger</i> (Simon, 1901)	4	LC	SAE	
	<i>Hyllus argyrotoxis</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Hyllus dotatus</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Massagris honesta</i> Wesolowska, 1993	4	LC	SAE	WC,EC
	<i>Menemerus bivittatus</i> (Dufour, 1831)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Myrmarachne laurentina</i> Bacelar, 1953	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Phintella aequipipes</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Pseudicius africanus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Rumburak hilaris</i> Wesolowska, Azarkina & Russell-Smith, 2014	4	LC	SAE	WC,EC
	<i>Tanzania</i> sp. 1 (imm.)			NE	
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thyene ogdeni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thyenula aurantiaca</i> (Simon, 1902)	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Thyenula cheliceroides</i> Wesolowska, Azarkina & Russell-Smith, 2014	3	LC	SAE	

continued

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND	PROV
	<i>Thyenula juvenca</i> Simon, 1902	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Thyenula tenebrica</i> Wesolowska, Azarkina & Russell-Smith, 2014	6	DD	SAE	ECE
	<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE	
Scytodidae	<i>Scytodes caffra</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Scytodes silvatica</i> Purcell, 1904	4	LC	SAE	WC,EC
Segestriidae	<i>Ariadna lightfooti</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE	
Selenopidae	<i>Anyphops braunsi</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Anyphops gilli</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Anyphops marshalli</i> (Pocock, 1902)	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Anyphops minor</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Anyphops parvulus</i> (Pocock, 1900)	4	DD	SAE	WC,EC
	<i>Anyphops regalis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	5	DD	SAE	WCE
Sicariidae	<i>Hexophthalma spatulata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	4	LC	SAE	WC,EC
	<i>Loxosceles spinulosa</i> Purcell, 1904	4	LC	SAE	WC,EC
Sparassidae	<i>Palystes castaneus</i> (Latreille, 1819)	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE	
Tetragnathidae	<i>Diphya foordi</i> Omelko, Marusik & Lyle, 2020	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Leucauge decorata</i> (Blackwall, 1864)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Leucauge levanderi</i> (Kulczynski, 1901)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Leucauge thomeensis</i> Kraus, 1960	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Pachygnatha</i> sp. 1 (imm.)		NE		
	<i>Tetragnatha ceylonica</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1869	0	LC	C	
Theraphosidae	<i>Harpactira cafreriana</i> (Walckenaer, 1837)	5	LC	SAE	WCE
	<i>Harpactira tigrina</i> Ausserer, 1875	4	LC	SAE	
	<i>Idiothele nigrofulva</i> (Pocock, 1898)	2	LC	STHE	
Theridiidae	<i>Argyrodes convivans</i> Lawrence, 1937	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Chorizopella tragardhi</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Episinus bilineatus</i> Simon, 1894	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Euryopsis funebris</i> (Hentz, 1850)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Latrodectus cinctus</i> Blackwall, 1865	0	LC	C	
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C	
	<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Rhomphaea nasica</i> (Simon, 1873)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C	
	<i>Steatoda foravae</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman & Müller, 1992	4	LC	SAE	WC,EC
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Tidarren scenicum</i> (Thorell, 1899)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Theridula</i> sp. 1 (new?)		NE		
Thomisidae	<i>Avelis hystriculus</i> Simon, 1895	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Camaricus nigrotesselatus</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Firmicus abnormis</i> (Lessert, 1923)	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Holopelus albibarbis</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Monaeses fuscus</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1984	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Monaeses paradoxus</i> (Lucas, 1864)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Mystaria lindaicapensis</i> Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014	4	VU	SAE	WC,EC
	<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	

continued

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND	PROV
Thomisidae	<i>Oxytate ribes</i> (Jézéquel, 1964)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Pactactes trimaculatus</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Parabomis martini</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Phaenopoma nigropunctatum</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1883)	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Pherecydes tuberculatus</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1883	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Phrynarachne melloleitaoi</i> Lessert, 1933	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Phrynarachne rugosa</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Runcinia erythrina</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Runcinia insecta</i> (L. Koch, 1875)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Runcinia johnstoni</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Simorcus haddadi</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2010	5	NT	SAE	WCE
	<i>Synema decens</i> (Karsch, 1878)	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Synema nigrotibiale</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thomisops sulcatus</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thomisus australis</i> Comellini, 1957	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thomisus kalaharinus</i> Lawrence, 1936	1	LC	AE	
	Trachelidae	<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900		1	LC	AE	
<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i> Millot, 1942		1	LC	AE	
<i>Tmarus comellinii</i> Garcia-Neto, 1989		1	LC	AE	
<i>Xysticus tugelanus</i> Lawrence, 1942		2	LC	STHE	
<i>Afrocto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)		2	LC	STHE	
<i>Capobula infima</i> (Simon, 1896)		5	LC	SAE	WCE
<i>Jocquestus capensis</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2018		5	DD	SAE	WCE
<i>Spinotrachelas capensis</i> Haddad, 2006		5	LC	SAE	WCE
<i>Thysanina transversa</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2006		3	LC	SAE	
Trochanteriidae	<i>Trachelas</i> sp. (imm.)		NE		
	<i>Platyoides walteri</i> (Karsch, 1887)	1	LC	AE	
Uloboridae	<i>Hyptiotes akermani</i> Wiehle, 1964	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C	
Zodariidae	<i>Zosis geniculata</i> (Olivier, 1789)	1	LC	C	
	<i>Chariobas lineatus</i> Pocock, 1900	4	LC	SAE	WC,EC
	<i>Cydrela</i> sp. 1 (new?)		NE		
	<i>Diores silvestris</i> Jocqué, 1990	5	Rare	SAE	WCE
	<i>Diores simoni</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	5	LC	SAE	WCE
	<i>Procydrela procursor</i> Jocqué, 1999	4	EN	SAE	WC,EC
	<i>Systemoplacis fagei</i> (Lawrence, 1937)	3	LC	SAE	
Zoropsidae	<i>Griswoldia acaenata</i> (Griswold, 1991)	4	LC	SAE	WC,EC
	<i>Griswoldia robusta</i> (Simon, 1898)	5	LC	SAE	WCE
	<i>Griswoldia sibyna</i> (Griswold, 1991)	5	DD	SAE	WCE
	<i>Phanotea cavata</i> Griswold, 1994	4	LC	SAE	WC,EC
	<i>Phanotea digitata</i> Griswold, 1994	5	LC	SAE	WCE
	<i>Phanotea knysna</i> Griswold, 1994	5	DD	SAE	WCE
	<i>Phanotea sathegyna</i> Griswold, 1994	5	DD	SAE	WCE
	<i>Phanotea xhosa</i> Griswold, 1994	4	LC	SAE	WC,EC

GEDENKSCHRIFT FOR PROF. STEFAN FOORD

On behalf of the guest editors, we would like to invite submissions for a special issue to be published in *African Invertebrates* in remembrance of our colleague, Prof. Stefan Hendrik Foord. At the time of his passing, he was the NRF-SARChI Chair in Biodiversity Value and Change at the University of Venda in South Africa, and was the sitting Chairperson of the African Arachnological Society (AFRAS). He was a prolific ecologist and did a lot of pioneering work on the biodiversity and ecology of spiders in South Africa, particularly. During his career, he published more than 100 journal articles, one book chapter, and two books. He was instrumental in the preparation of the First Atlas of South African Spiders, the Red List of South African Spiders, and the recently published national spider checklist. He also made a significant contribution to the systematics of Afrotropical spiders, revising the Hersiliidae as his Ph.D. study, and described or co-authored the description of 29 spider species during his career.

In honouring and celebrating the contributions of Stefan to African biology, a Gedenkschrift will be published in the journal *African Invertebrates* in December 2024. Priority will be given to manuscripts in the following fields:

- Taxonomy of African arthropods,
- Ecology of African arthropods,
- Biogeography of African arthropods and
- Other manuscripts within the journal scope celebrating Stefan's legacy.

GUEST EDITORS

Galina Azarkina (Collection editor); Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman; Charles Haddad; Robin Lyle; John Midgley; Caswell Munyai.

SUBMISSION PROCESS

To pitch a contribution to this Gedenkschrift, either contact the Editor-in-Chief (John Midgley, johnmidge@gmail.com) or the collection editor (Galina Azarkina, urmakuz@gmail.com). There is no limit to the length of submitted manuscripts. The deadline for submission is 30 September 2024. No late submissions will be accepted.

Contributing authors are required to follow the general formatting guidelines for *African Invertebrates* (<https://africaninvertebrates.pensoft.net/about#AuthorGuidelines>). Contributing authors who are not native English speakers are requested to send their contributions to an English-speaking colleague or language-editing service to improve the linguistic quality of their submissions.

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GENERAL: We look forward to your contributions to this special issue, which was organized to honour our late colleague and friend, Stefan Foord. Please note that submitting a manuscript does not automatically mean it will be included – ALL submissions will be subjected to critique by at least two suitably qualified reviewers, and poor quality manuscripts rejected by the Guest Editors or reviewers will not be further considered for this issue.